

Assessment of Parental Socio-Demographic Determinants on Sexual Abuse among Senior Secondary School Students in Benin Educational Zone, Edo State

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Abstract

This study assessed parental socio-demographic determinants on sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo state. Three research questions and hypotheses were raised to guide the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design and the population of the study comprised all public and register private senior secondary schools in Benin educational zone. The multi-staged sampling technique was used to select 184 male students and 200 female students making a total of 384 respondents for the study. A Self-structured questionnaire titled “Sexual Abuse among Secondary School Students (SASSS)” was used for the collection of data. The research instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.73 was obtained using the test-retest reliability method. Data obtained were analyzed using chi-square inferential statistics. Findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. Similarly, the study established a significant relationship between parental socio-economic status and family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The researchers concluded that parental socio-economic status and family size are socio-demographic determinants on the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone. On the contrary, marital status is not a parental socio-demographic determinant on the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone. The researchers recommended that government and non-governmental agencies should develop support programs for families from lower socio-economic backgrounds.

Keywords: Parental socio-demographic, determinants, socioeconomic status, sexual abuse, students.

Introduction

The sexual abuse of children has been categorized by different researchers across the world as representing a global human rights violation of children with severe immediate and long-term health and social consequences (Hillis, James, Amobi, & Kress, 2016). Despite being a global epidemic, there is considerable debate over what exactly constitutes the sexual abuse of children. The variation in definitions is due to sexual abuse being a complex issue (De Jong, et al., 2015; Samms & Cholewa, 2014) and the definitions of CSA differ between cultures and societies (Meinck, et al, 2015). Different cultures have their standards by which sexual behaviours towards children are considered and judged as acceptable or deplorable. For instance, in a typical African culture, love and affection for children may be expressed by their parents, relatives and friends through various forms of touch or practices that may be seen as sexually stimulating in another culture, particularly in the Western culture. Hence, it is crucial to employ culturally appropriate definitions when assessing child sexual abuse.

Sexual abuse of children is a grave and pervasive violation of human rights that continues to plague societies worldwide, transcending cultural, geographic, and socio-economic boundaries. It encompasses a range of acts, from sexual exploitation and molestation to trafficking and forced pornography, all of which have devastating and lasting effects on the physical, psychological, and emotional well-being of children. In Nigeria, like many other countries, child sexual abuse remains a significant and deeply concerning issue, demanding urgent attention and targeted interventions. In Nigeria, community-based surveys among in-school and out-of-school adolescents indicated high levels of CSA. In a study from Maiduguri, North-East Nigeria, a sexual assault rate of 77.7% was reported among female children’s workers with sexual assault being more likely in girls who were younger than twelve (12) years (Audu, et al., 2009). Also, Kunnuji and Essiet (2015) reported that about 14% and 35% of out of school adolescents in an urban slum in Lagos had been victims of rape and statutory rape, respectively. Olley (2008) and Manyike, et al. (2015) reported a child sexual abuse (CSA) prevalence of 55% and 40% among in-school

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adolescents in Southwest and South-east Nigeria, respectively. Other studies based on newspaper accounts indicate a high incidence of sexual abuse of children in different parts of Nigeria (Okonkwo & Naish, 2013; Akpoghome & Nwano, 2016).

Several socio-demographic factors are known to play a pivotal role in shaping the vulnerability of school children to child sexual abuse. Parental attributes, including marital status, family size and socioeconomic economic status may significantly influence a child's risk of falling victim to sexual abuse. Parental socioeconomic status has been cited as a determinant of sexual abuse of children. The socioeconomic status involves family income, education and occupational status. Specifically, on parental level of education predicting sexual abuse of children, Chime, Orji, Aneke and Nwoke (2021) revealed that the prevalence of CSA is higher among students whose parents achieved secondary school education and above than those with primary school education and below. In contrast, Abodunrin, et al. (2014) reported that children from parents with secondary and tertiary level of education were less likely to experience sexual abuse than the less educated ones. For example, lower levels of education in fathers may be correlated with increased risk of child sexual abuse in some populations or settings. This could be due to various reasons, such as lower education levels being associated with increased stress, financial difficulties, mental health issues, and other risk factors that may impact parenting behaviours and family dynamics (Brown & Williams, 2016).

On the relationship between maternal educational level and sexual abuse of children, Johnson and Stone (2014) suggest that a mother's level of education could potentially impact child sexual abuse risk factors in different ways. For example, higher education levels may be associated with increased awareness of child sexual abuse prevention strategies, better access to resources, and improved parenting skills, which may potentially reduce the risk of child sexual abuse. On the other hand, lower education levels may be associated with increased stress, limited access to resources, and other challenges, which may potentially increase the risk of sexual abuse of children. In explaining the higher prevalence rate of sexual abuse of children across higher educational level, Akinsulire (2017) stated that parents with higher educational qualifications tend to have better employment opportunities as they work outside the family setting, exposing their children to sexual abuse through lack of parental protection and supervision. On the relationship between parental employment status and the prevalence rate of sexual abuse of children, Abera et al. (2021) reported that adolescents whose fathers were self-employed or salaried were more up to five times more likely to be sexually abused and this may be attributed to the fact that such fathers had better employment opportunities and so were away from home (Akinsulire, 2017).

Furthermore, parents' income influences the incidence of abuse of children including child sexual abuse. Hurst (2021) illustrated that children from families seeking financial assistance were over two times more likely to suffer for child labour and sexually abused. In line with this, Okpukpara (2015) reported that the incident of child abuse including child sexual abuse was high among learners whose parents' income was N50,000 and below. It was to a low extent for learners whose parents' income was N51,000 and above. The finding was in consonance with that of Elgbeleye and Olasupol (2011) who found out that parents of low-income status showed significant high tendencies toward child labour practices (which is a predisposing factor for sexual abuse of children) than their high-income counterparts. In general, Sedlak, Mettenburg, Basena et al. (2010) report that children from families with low SES were twice as likely to experience sexual abuse and three times more likely to be endangered than children from families with higher SES. In a recent study, Lee, Coe and Ryff (2017) report a higher risk of severe and multiple types of sexual abuse for children experiencing poverty during childhood. However, Oshima, Jonson-Reid and Seay (2014) found no significant difference in the rate of sexual abuse of children from more affluent and poor families.

Additionally, family size has also been cited as a predictor of sexual abuse of children. The number of children in a family was shown to be significantly associated with sexual abuse of children (Schoedl et al., 2010). In investigating the prevalence of child sexual abuse among secondary school adolescents in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria Gabriel-Job, Alikor and Akani (2019) reported that the prevalence of sexual abuse of children increased significantly from 30.9% in those that came from families of four children or less to 43.9% in those from families of more than four children. Corroborating this finding, Farah (2010) also reported that children who were abused were found to come from families who had significantly more children. A possible explanation for this finding could be that every additional child to the family leads to an increase in financial burden as well as an increase in the likelihood of the children engaging in child labour to financially support their parents thus increasing their vulnerability to child sexual abuse. Also, there seems to be a relationship between family disruption and the prevalence of sexual abuse of children. This view is corroborated by previous studies on family disruption and history of CSA (Fomby & Cherlin 2007; Li & Wu, 2008) where the role of a stable family in preventing sexual abuse of children was highlighted. Disruptions of family structure either by death or divorce may reduce parental control during childhood and adolescence thereby making children more exposed to potential child sexual abuse perpetrators (Yahaya, 2012).

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Conclusively, in societies worldwide, including the African context, parents universally uphold the belief that children are the most treasured assets and the bearers of tomorrow's hope. This cherished philosophy underlines the imperative of nurturing a childhood marked by happiness and devoid of crises, uncertainties, and danger. Regrettably, despite the deeply rooted commitment by government and non-governmental agencies to nurturing and safeguarding children, Sexual abuse of school children still lingers as an acute social dilemma, and an egregious violation of human rights that continues to undermine the well-being of children across the world. In light of this disconcerting dissonance between the cherished philosophy of childhood and the persistently distressing prevalence of sexual abuse, it becomes imperative to comprehensively investigate the parental socio-demographic determinants that contribute to this grave issue particularly within the context of Benin educational zone of Edo State, Nigeria, as understanding how parental socio-demographic factors intersect with the occurrence of sexual abuse is essential for formulating effective and targeted interventions.

Objectives of the study

The objective of the study was to assess the parental socio-demographic determinants on sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. Specifically, the study investigated:

1. The relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.
2. The relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.
3. The relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?
2. What is the relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?
3. What is the relationship between socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.
2. There is no significant relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.
3. There is no significant relationship parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The descriptive research design accurately and systematically describes, observes or validates aspects of groups collected through quantifiable information without manipulation of the variables (Siedlecki, 2020). Based on Siedlecki (2020) description of the descriptive survey research design, the researcher was able to use this design to effectively provide an in-depth assessment of the socio-demographic determinants on sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The population of the study comprised all the public and registered private senior secondary schools in the seven (7) local government areas that make up the Benin Educational Zone. The total population of public senior secondary school student is thirty-one thousand, seven hundred and twenty-five (31,725) while that of registered private senior secondary school is seventy-five thousand, five hundred and forty-seven (75,547). This gives a total population of one hundred and seven thousand, two hundred and seventy-one (107,271) senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone (Edo state Ministry of Education, 2022). Sample size of 384 respondents was selected using the Cochran's formulae. The sample was selected using multi-stage sampling technique. In the first stage, three (3) Local Government Areas was selected from the seven (7) Local Government Areas in Edo South senatorial district of Edo using simple random sampling technique of balloting by replacement. In the second stage, stratified random sampling technique was used to group the schools into rural school and urban school based on their location.

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In the third stage, Two (2) schools (one public urban school and one public rural school) were selected from each of the three Local Government Areas using simple random sampling technique of balloting by replacement. Lastly, simple random sampling technique of balloting by replacement was used to select 18 female respondents and 14 male respondents from each of the six selected schools. The same procedure was repeated to select sample from the registered private schools.

Table 1: Sample distribution

S/N	School Type	No. of schools selected	No. of school children selected	
			Male	Female
1.	Public Urban Schools	3	46	50
2.	Public Rural Schools	3	46	50
3.	Private Urban Schools	3	46	50
4.	Private Rural Schools	3	46	50
	Total	12	184	200
	Grand total			384

The research instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Sexual Abuse among Secondary School Students (SASSS)”. The instrument has two sections: sections A and B. Section A sought the socio-demographic information of the respondents, while Section B sought the parental socio-demographic information of respondents. However, items on parental socio-economic status were adapted from Gaur’s socio-economic classification (2013). The instrument was content validated, and a reliability index of 0.73 was obtained using the test-retest reliability method, thereafter subjecting the scores obtained from both administrations of the instrument to Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Socio-demographic variables were coded thus: marital status (married=1, separated =2, divorced=3 widowed=4); family size (1-2 children=2, 3-4 children =4, 5 children and above=6) and socio-economic status (positively worded question, yes=1point, no=0point; negatively worded question, yes= 0point, no=1point). Marital status was further measured as intact and disrupted family; family size was measured as small, moderate and large family size and socio-economic status was further measured as Upper, Middle and Lower Class.

The research instrument was administered by the researcher and three research assistants who were trained on the objectives of the research. The research instrument was administered after seeking due permission from the school principals. Also, the respondents were briefed on the purpose of the study alongside a general overview of child sexual abuse. The respondents were assured of utmost confidentiality regarding their responses and administered questionnaires were retrieved immediately upon completion after checking to ensure their level of completeness by respondents. This enabled the researcher to obtain a 100percent return rate. The collected data was coded and analyzed using frequency counts, simple percentages and Chi-square inferential statistics.

Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Benin Teach hospital Research and Ethic Committee and a formal permission to allow the selected schools to participate in the research was requested and granted through the Commissioner of Education and Principals of each of the selected schools. To maintain confidentiality of the respondents, respondents were asked not to indicate their names on the questionnaires.)

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?

Table 2: Descriptive statistics on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384)

S/N	Parental marital status	Sexual Abuse	
		Yes	No
		f (%)	f (%)

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1.	Married	143 (37.24%)	84 (21.88%)
2.	Separated	56 (14.58%)	33 (8.59%)
3.	Divorced	15 (3.91%)	15 (3.91%)
4.	Widowed	26 (6.77%)	12 (3.12%)
	Total	240	144

(Researchers' fieldwork, 2023)

Table 2 reveals the descriptive statistics on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. It can be observed that 143(37.24%) respondents who had been sexually abused indicated that their parents were married. Also, 56(14.58%), 15(3.91%) and 26 (6.77%) respondents who had been sexually abused indicated that their parents were separated, divorced and widowed respectively. Therefore, it can be deduced that the parents of majority of the respondents who have experienced sexual abuse were married.

Research Question 2:

What is the relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?

Table 3: Descriptive statistics on the relationship between relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384)

S/N	Family Size	Sexual Abuse	
		Yes f (%)	No f (%)
1.	1-2 children	95 (24.74%)	40 (10.42%)
2.	3-4 children	109 (28.39%)	92 (23.96%)
3.	4 children above	36 (9.38%)	12 (3.12%)
	Total	240	144

(Researchers' fieldwork, 2023)

Table 3 reveals the descriptive statistics on the relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. It can be observed that 95(24.74%) respondents who had been sexually abused indicated had a family size of 1-2 children. Also, 109 (28.39%) and 36(9.38%) respondents who had been sexually abused indicated that have a family size of 3-4 children and 4 children and above respectively. Therefore, it can be deduced that majority of the respondents who have experienced sexual abuse had a family size of 3-4 children.

Research Question 3:

What is the relationship between socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State?

Table 4: Descriptive statistics on the relationship between socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384)

S/N	Socio-economic status	Sexual Abuse	
		Yes f (%)	No f (%)
1.	Upper Class	30 (7.81%)	23(5.99%)
2.	Middle Class	142 (36.98%)	87 (22.66%)
3.	Lower Class	68 (17.71%)	34 (8.85%)
	Total	240	144

Source: Researchers' fieldwork

Table 4 reveals the descriptive statistics on the relationship between socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. It can be observed that 30(7.81%) respondents who had been sexually abused belong to the Upper Class while 142(36.98%) and 68(17.71%) respondents who have been sexually

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abused belong to Middle Class and Lower Class respectively. It can be deduced therefore, that majority of the respondents who have experienced sexual abuse are from the Middle Class.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant relationship between parental marital status and the sexual abuse among school children in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State

Table 5: Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384).

S/N	Marital status	Sexual Abuse		χ^2	df	Sig.
		Yes O(E)	No O(E)			
1.	Intact family	143(141.9)	84(85.1)	0.058	1	0.110
2.	Disrupted family	97(98.1)	60(58.9)			

1point=intact family, 2-9points=disrupted family; P>0.05

Table 5 shows the Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The table indicates a calculated chi-square value of 0.058, degree of freedom 1 and level of significance of 0.110 which is greater than the set alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo state is retained. The table clearly indicates no significant differences in the number of respondents (143) from intact family (a family where both parent are still married) who had experienced child sexual abuse and respondents (97) from disrupted family (a family where both parent are no longer together due to separation, divorce or death) who had also been sexually abused. The conclusion here therefore, is that there is no significant relationship between parental marital status and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Table 6 shows the Chi-square analysis on the relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Table 6: Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental marital status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384).

S/N	Family size	Sexual Abuse		χ^2	df	Sig.
		Yes O(E)	No O(E)			
1.	Small family size	95(84.4)	40(50.6)	12.63	2	0.002
1.	Moderate family size	109(125.6)	92(75.4)			
2.	Large family size	36(30)	12(18)			

2points=small family size, 4points=moderate family size, 6points=large family size; P=<0.05

secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The table indicates a calculated chi-square value of 12.63, degree of freedom 2 and level of significance of 0.002 which is lesser than the set alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between family size and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State is rejected. The table clearly shows a significant difference in the number of respondents (95) from small family size (a family of 1-2 children) who had experienced sexual abuse and respondents (145) from moderate and large family size (a family of 3-4 children and 4 children and above, respectively) who had also have been sexually abused. The conclusion here therefore, is that there is a significant relationship between family size and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

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Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant relationship between parental socio-demographic socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State

Table 7: Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State (n=384)

S/N	Socio-economic status	Sexual Abuse		χ^2	df	Sig.
		Yes O(E)	No O(E)			
1.	Upper Class	30(17.44)	23(10.56)	32.32	2	0.001
2.	Middle Class	142(113.35)	87(68.65)			
3.	Lower Class	68(53.21)	34(32.1)			

15-23points=Upper Class, 5-14points=Middle Class, 0-4points=Lower Class; P<0.05

Table 7 shows the Chi-square analysis on the relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. The table indicates a calculated chi-square value of 32.32, degree of freedom 2 and level of significance of 0.001 which is lesser than the set alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State is rejected. The table clearly indicates a significant difference in the number of respondents from upper class (30), middle class (142) and lower class (68) that had experienced sexual abuse as against those who haven't. The conclusion here therefore, is that there is a significant relationship between parental socio-economic status and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State

Discussion of Findings

On parental marital status, findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between parental marital status and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. In line with this, this study revealed no significant differences in the number of respondents from intact family who had experienced child sexual abuse and respondents from disrupted family who had also been sexually abused. This view is contrary to findings from previous studies (Fomby & Cherlin 2007; Li & Wu, 2012) which indicated a significant relationship between family disruption and history of CSA. The researcher attributes this contrary finding to the fact that sexual abuse is a multifactorial phenomenon influenced by a variety of factors such as the respondents' individual and environmental characteristics. Hence, the respondents' individual and environmental characteristics may better predispose them to sexual than parental marital status.

Furthermore, findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between family size and the occurrence of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. In line with this, this study established a significant difference in the number of respondents that had experienced sexual abuse and those who did not based on their family size. Specifically, respondents from moderate and large family size experienced sexual abuse more than those from small family size. This finding is similar to the findings of Gabriel-Job, Alikor and Akani (2019) who reported that the prevalence of sexual abuse increased significantly from 30.9% in those that came from families of four children or less to 43.9% in those from families of more than four children. Family size being a predisposing factor may be attributed to the fact that large family families may face additional stressors related to financial, mental and emotional demands, which could impact family dynamics and increase the risk of sexual abuse. High levels of stress, lack of resources, and other challenges may affect parental capacity to effectively protect their children and create an environment that is conducive to healthy child development. Conclusively, a significant relationship between parental socio-economic status and sexual abuse was established by this study. This finding is similar to the findings of Sedlak et al. (2010) who report that children from families with low SES were twice as likely to experience sexual abuse and three times more likely to be endangered than children from families with higher SES. In contrast, Oshima, Jonson-Reid and Seay (2014) found no significant relationship between SES and child sexual abuse. The researcher noted that the high prevalence of sexual in respondents from low socio-economic status may be due to several factors including the lack of resources in schools and other institutions serving low income communities to identify, prevent and respond to cases of sexual abuse. Also, families living in poverty may often face high level of stress and may experience violence, substance abuse or other problems that can increase the risk of child sexual abuse.

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Conclusion

This study provides insights into the parental socio-demographic determinants on sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo state. Based on the findings of this study, the researchers concluded that marital status is not a parental socio-demographic determinant of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State. However, family size and parental socio-economic status are parental socio-demographic determinants of sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Benin educational zone, Edo State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were made:

1. There should be a prioritization of research into potential determinants of sexual abuse among school children such as family size and parental socio-economic status.
2. Government and non-governmental agencies should develop and implement community-based support systems that offer assistance and guidance to families with larger family sizes, helping them navigate the challenges that may contribute to child sexual abuse. Also, schools in collaboration with parents and caregivers should develop programs that provide parents with strategies for maintaining a safe and protective environment within larger families while emphasizing communication, supervision, and recognizing signs of abuse.
3. Government and non-governmental agencies should develop programs that aim to uplift families from lower socio-economic backgrounds, providing them with access to education, employment opportunities, and financial support. Also, the program should include an offer of educational workshops for parents from lower socio-economic backgrounds that focus on child protection, healthy parenting practices, and recognizing signs of abuse.

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References

- Abera, L., Aliye, A., Tadesse, K. & Guta, A. (2021). Magnitude of child sexual abuse and its associated factors among high school female students in Dire Dawa, Eastern Ethiopia: A cross-sectional study. *Reproductive Health Journal*, 18, 224.
- Abodunrin, O. L., Adeoye, O. A., Adeomi, A. A., & Akande, T. M. (2014). Prevalence and forms of violence against health care professionals in a South-Western city, Nigeria. *Sky Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 2(8):067 - 072.
- Akinsulire, O. O. (2017). A comparative study on prevalence, pattern and determinants of sexual abuse amongst adolescents in selected slum and non-slum communities in Lagos State. [PhDThesis, National Postgraduate Medical College of Nigeria]. 104-115.
- Akpoghome, T. U., & Nwano, T. (2016). Examining the incidences of sexual defilement of children in Nigeria. *Donnish Journal of Law and Conflict Resolution* 2(1):001-009.
- Audu, B., Geidam, A., & Jarma, H. (2009). Child labour and sexual assault among girls in Maiduguri, Nigeria. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 104, 64–67.
- Chime, O. H., Orji, C. J., Aneke, T. J., & Nwoke, I. N. (2021). Prevalence, pattern and predictors of child sexual abuse among senior secondary school students in Enugu Metropolis. *Malays Journal of Medical Science*, 28(4):123–137.
- De Jong, R., Alink, L., Bijleveld, C., Finkenauer, C., & Hendriks, J. (2015). Transition to adulthood of child sexual abuse victims. *Aggression and violent behaviour*, 24(184):175-187.
- Elgbeleye O. S., & Olasupo M. O. (2011). Parental socio-economic status as correlate of child labour in Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *Bangladesh e-Journal of Sociology*, 8 (2):137–146.
- Farah, M. (2010). Determinants of child abuse in pakistani families: Parental acceptance-rejection and demographic variables. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 1(1).
- Fomby, P., & Cherlin, A. J. (2007). *Family instability and child well-being*. *American Sociological Review*, 72(2): 181–204.
- Gabriel-Job, N., Alikor, G. N., & Akani, N. A. (2019). Prevalence of child sexual abuse among secondary school adolescents in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Paediatrics*, 46(4):156-162.
- Gaur, K. L. (2013). Socio-economic Status Measurement Scale: Thirst Area with Changing Concept for Socio-Economic Status. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 2(9):139-145.
- Hillis, S., Mercy, J., Amobi, A., & Kress, H. (2016). Global prevalence of past-year violence against children: A systematic review and minimum estimates. *Nigerian Journal of Paediatrics*, 137, e20154079.

Assessment of Parental Socio-Demograph... (Aideyan & Odigie, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10020163>

- Kunnuji MO, Esiet A. (2015). Prevalence and correlates of sexual abuse among female out-of- school adolescents in Iwaya Community, Lagos State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 19(1):82-90.
- Lee, C., Coe, C. L., & Ryff, C. D. (2017). Social disadvantage, severe child abuses and biological profiles in adulthood. *Journal of Health and Social Behaviour*, 58, 371–386.
- Li, L. J.-C. A., & Wu, L. L. (2008). No trend in the intergenerational transmission of divorce. *Demography*, 45(4): 875–883
- Manyike, P. C., Chinawa, J. M., Aniwada, E., Odutola, O. I., & Chinawa, T. A. (2015). Child sexual abuse among adolescents in Southeast Nigeria: A concealed public health behavioural issue. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 31(4): 827–832.
- Meinck, F., Cluver, L. D., Boyes, M. E., & Mhlongo, E. L. (2015). Risk and protective factors for physical and sexual abuse of children and adolescents in Africa: A review and implications for practice. *Trauma, violence, and abuse*, 16(1): 81-107.
- Okonkwo, O., & Naish, M. E. (2013). *Criminal Law in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Spectrum Publisher.
- Olley, B. O. (2008). Child sexual abuse, harmful alcohol use and age as determinants of sexual risk behaviours among freshmen in a Nigerian University. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 12, 75-88.
- Oshima, K. M. M., Jonson-Reid, M., Seay, K. D. (2014). The influence of childhood sexual abuse on adolescent outcomes: the role of gender, poverty and revictimization. *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse*, 23, 367–386.
- Schoedl , A. F., Costa, M. C. P., Mari, J. J., Mello, M. F., Tyrka , A.R., Carpenter , L. L., & Price, L. H. (2010). The clinical correlates of reported childhood sexual abuse: An association between age at trauma onset and severity of depression and PTSD in adults. *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse*, 19(2): 156–170.
- Sedlak, A. J., Mettenburg, J., Basena, M., Petta, I., McPherson, K., & Greene, A. (2014). Fourth National Incidence Study of Child Abuse and Neglect (NIS–4): Report to congress. U.S department of health and human services, administration for children and families; Washington, DC, USA.
- Yahaya. I. (2012). A comparative study of the socioeconomic factors associated with childhood sexual abuse in sub-Saharan Africa. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 11(51): 51.